

SEISMEC

NEWSWAVE

Dear reader,

With summer just around the corner, we welcome you to our third official newsletter!

We're excited to share the latest updates and insights from the [SEISMEC](#) project, as we've undertaken significant activities over the past six months, reached key milestones, and are now preparing for an impactful autumn.

In this issue, we provide a comprehensive overview of our [Pilots](#) and [Solution](#) Directions. Two major project milestones. We continue with key insights from our first online workshop and our reflections from the last General Assembly meeting in Cork, Ireland. News and updates from our sister projects are also included, and what a nicer way to wrap up this issue than learning about our past and future events.

[We know that we've sparked your curiosity. Stay with us and enjoy the journey through this edition!](#)

The SEISMEC Pilot Journey has begun!

We are pleased to announce that the [SEISMEC pilots](#) have begun, with some initial results already generated!

At the heart of SEISMEC lies a diverse and dynamic collection of piloting activities, which are essential in shaping the project's scope and outcomes.

These pilots unfold our efforts to integrate cutting-edge technology with human-centric approaches, grounded in the insights of social sciences and humanities. Through this integration, SEISMEC aims to empower workers, support the co-design of innovative tools, and foster a more resilient and inclusive industrial ecosystem.

Throughout the project, [a total of 17 pilots will be conducted across 14 countries](#), focusing on a wide range of strategic areas.

[EXPLORE THE SEISMEC PILOTS](#)

Solution Directions

[LEARN MORE](#)

SEISMEC provides a carefully developed set of Solution Directions, comprising design methods, technologies, and instruments, designed to advance human-centric innovation. Co-created with stakeholders and shaped by expert insight, these solutions support organisations in tackling evolving workplace challenges and adopting new technologies in ways that place people at the centre.

SEISMEC Online Workshop

Our first online workshop was held on May 15th, 2025, with the presence of interested internal and external stakeholders. Under the title "[Human Centric Industry 5.0 - Concepts and Solutions](#)," we explored innovative concepts and practical, human-centric solutions that are shaping a more inclusive, sustainable, and resilient future for industry and society.

The two key presentations were on "Industry 5.0: Why the shift and what it means for the future of work", from [Mirela Mărcuț \(Transilvania IT Cluster\)](#) and [Anne Vries \(TNO\)](#), who presented the Solution Directions, their design guidelines and real-world examples.

[WATCH FULL RECORDING](#)

[EXPLORE OUR KNOWLEDGE PILLS](#)

SEISMEC GA Reflections

On April 7-8, 2025, the SEISMEC consortium partners travelled to Cork, Ireland, for the project's second General Assembly, hosted by [University College Cork](#). This two-day meeting offered a meaningful opportunity to review progress, exchange insights, and collaboratively plan the project's next phase.

[INSIDE THE GENERAL ASSEMBLY](#)

SEISMEC presents!

In this exclusive interview series, we asked our project's [Work Package leaders](#) to discuss their roles, progress, and insights. Each leader gives a brief overview of their WP, its connection to the broader project, and the current status and future roadmap.

In our first episodes, we are hearing from [Chantal Ho](#) ([Erasmus University Rotterdam](#)) about [Work Package 1, "Framework for Human-Centric Assessment,"](#) [Ilias Koulalis](#) ([CERTH](#)) about [Work Package 2, "Tools and methods towards human-centrism"](#) and [Siobhan O'Neill](#) ([UCC](#)) about [Work Package 4, "Transversal Pilot analyses."](#)

[Work Package 1](#)
Chantal Ho

[Work Package 2](#)
Ilias Koulalis

[Work Package 4](#)
Siobhan O'Neill

News and updates from our [sister Projects](#) [Bridges 5.0](#)

[Bridges 5.0: building an accelerated pathway to Industry 5.0](#)

Bridges 5.0 is an EU HORIZON project focused on the transition to Industry 5.0, supporting businesses, workers and society by addressing skills gaps, promoting learning and development, and facilitating wider understanding of its economic and social potential. Take a look at their [website](#) where you can

discover their [publications](#), be inspired by a growing body of articles on aspects of Industry 5.0, and register for the webinar programme. You can also join the Industry 5.0 Platform, a place where you can access knowledge and resources, share ideas and experiences, join discussions, and connect with a wide range of practitioners and experts. You'll also be part of the wider Fresh Thinking Labs community, enabling you to explore many other topics relating to the future of work.

PROSPECTS 5.0

From Vision to Implementation: Insights from the PROSPECTS 5.0 Workshop Series

In the first half of 2025, the [PROSPECTS 5.0](#) project hosted a workshop series to promote shared learning and collaboration around the adoption of Industry 5.0 across European industries. These workshops, held both online and in-person, brought together over 50 participants from across Europe, including partners, use

case providers, and external stakeholders. The [first workshop, held in March 2025](#), aimed to foster cross-sectoral dialogue and knowledge sharing around practical implementation of Industry 5.0.

Prospect 5.0 use cases-companies from various sectors and regions of Europe shared their experiences, highlighting common challenges such as resistance to change, high integration costs, and skills shortages. Despite these hurdles, participants demonstrated tangible benefits from Industry 5.0 adoption, including enhanced efficiency, quality, and resilience, through tools such as AI-assisted systems and predictive maintenance. The [second workshop](#), held in May in Mirandola, Italy, shifted focus to progress and integration, with presentations from use cases Teknorot (Turkey) and Knowit (Norway) illustrating ongoing efforts to embed Industry 5.0 into broader business strategy.

Participants reflected on the role of the Industry 5.0 Assessment Framework in sparking internal dialogue and guiding KPI alignment, especially around human-centricity. Discussions also emphasised the critical role of external enablers, such as policy support and sustainability-driven customer demands, in accelerating transformation.

Across both sessions, a consensus emerged: Industry 5.0 is more than a technological shift, it is becoming a strategic imperative. As companies embed their principles into their long-term plans, PROSPECTS 5.0 project continues to act as a key platform for fostering collaborative, future-ready industrial innovation in Europe.

AI REGIO 5.0

AI REDGIO 5.0 - Unlocking AI-at-the-Edge for manufacturing transformation towards Industry 5.0

AI REDGIO 5.0 aims to accelerate the digital transformation of manufacturing SMEs by helping them integrating AI-at-the-Edge and Industry 5.0 systems. The project focuses on developing AI-driven solutions that enhance operational efficiency, sustainability and human-centred practices. It will support Industry 5.0 test-before-invest experiments in AI Didactic Factories, Virtual Factories, and TEFs (Testing and Experimentation Facilities), as well as SME-driven experiments.

SEISMEC on the road!

Future and past events

From insightful workshops to major events, the SEISMEC consortium partners never miss an opportunity to present the project, its aims and scope to diverse audiences.

[READ OUR STORIES](#)

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